

Complex formation of some 3d-metal(II) ions with anthranilic acid *N,N*-diacetic acid in the absence and in the presence of some typical bidentate (N,N), (N,O⁻) and (O⁻,O⁻) donor ligands

G. N. Mukherjee*, Susmita Bandyopadhyay and Ansuman Das

Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta, University College of Science, 92 Acharya Prafulla Chandra Road, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : gurunath@cucc.ernet.in Fax : 91-033-3519755

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pH-metric investigation on the complex formation equilibria of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} (M^{II}) with anthranilic acid *N,N*-diacetic acid (H₃ada) in the absence and presence of 1,10-phenanthroline (phen), bipyridine (bipy), ethylenediamine (en), glycinate (gly⁻) and oxalate (ox²⁻) (B) in aqueous solution at 25 ± 1° at a fixed ionic strength, I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃) indicates the formation of simple binary complexes M(ada) and M(B) and ternary complexes M(ada)(B). M(ada)(B) complexes are formed according to equilibria M(B) + adaH ⇌ M(ada)(B) + H, with B = phen and bipy, and M(ada) + BH ⇌ M(ada)(B) + H, with B = en, gly⁻ and ox²⁻ ligands. Stability constants of the complexes have been evaluated by computerized method.

Mixed ligand complexes derived from transition metal ions with designed ligands having specific functional groups are useful in biomimetic studies for exploring the role of metal ions in enzymatic processes¹. *N*-Substituted-aminocarboxylic acids derived from amino acids, small peptides and related ligands containing other biologically relevant functional groups although provide ample scope for such model studies, no systematic study on the complex formation of such ligands with metal ions has yet been made. With a view to study systematically the formation, structure, stability and reactivity of complexes derived from these group of ligands, we describe here the results of a pH-metric equilibrium study on the complex formation of anthranilic acid *N,N*-diacetic acid (H₃ada) with Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions in the absence and in the presence of typical (N,N), (N,O) and (O⁻,O⁻) donor bidentate ligands, viz. 1,10-phenanthroline (phen), bipyridine (bipy), ethylenedi-amine (en), glycinate (gly⁻) and oxalate (ox²⁻) in aqueous solution at 25 ± 1° at a constant ionic strength I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃).

Results and discussion

Complex formation of M^{II} ions (M = Co, Ni, Cu and Zn) with the ligand H₃ada (H₃A) in the absence and in the presence of phen, bipy, en, gly⁻ and ox²⁻ ligands (B) may be represented by the general equilibria,

$$\beta_{pqrs} = \frac{[M_p(A)_q(B)_r(OH)_s]}{([M]^p [A]^q [B]^r [OH]^s)} \quad (1b)$$

where, the stoichiometric numbers *p*, *q* and *r* are positive integers or zero, *s* is a negative integer for a protonated species, positive integer for a deprotonated or a hydroxo species and zero for a normal species. The overall formation constants, β_{pqr^s}, may be calculated with the aid of the SCOGS² program and using these values the other relevant constants may be calculated using suitable relations.

The ligand H₃ada titrates as a triprotic acid (Fig. 1) due to successive deprotonation of the three COOH groups in the pH range 2–8. Comparatively weaker acidity of Hada²⁻ is possibly due to stabilization of this dianion by a unique type of hydrogen bonding (1),

Binary M^{II} : H₃ada equilibria :

In the presence of M^{II} ions, the buffer regions corresponding to the deprotonation equilibria of H₃ada are shifted to lower pH values (pH 2–4) at which practically no hydroxo metal species are found to be formed with any of these metal ions. Predominant metal containing species in

this pH range are the free M^{2+} (aq) ions and the binary 1 : 1 complexes, $M(ada)^-$, formed according to the equilibrium (2),

Consequently, two moles of base per mole of M^{2+} are consumed in this pH range.

1 : 1 : 1 $M^{II} : H_3ada : B$ ternary equilibria ($B = phen, bipy, en, gly^-, ox^{2-}$):

1 : 1 : 1 $M^{II} : H_3ada : B$ ratio was maintained throughout to ensure the exclusive formation of the simplest ternary complexes, $M(ada)(B)$. Free M^{2+} ions are practically non-existent from the very beginning of complex formation in the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary systems with $B = phen$ and $bipy$. The major metal containing species at the start of the reaction (pH ~2) are the $M(B)^{2+}$ complexes, which with rise of pH react with H_3ada^- and $Hada^{2-}$ to produce the ternary $M(B)(ada)^-$ complexes according to equilibria (3) and (4) as the speciation curves (not shown) imply,

$M(ada)^-$ complexes, formed according to equilibrium (2) are the predominant metal containing species at the early stages (pH 2–5) of complex formation in the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary $M^{2+} : H_3ada : B$ ($en/gly^-/ox^{2-}$) systems (figures not shown). Neither the binary $M(B)$ complexes nor any hydroxometal complex are identifiable in the entire pH range (2–10) of complexes formation in these systems. The ternary $M(ada)(B)$ complex (charges not shown for simplicity) are formed above pH~5 according to equilibrium (5),

and represent the major metal containing species above pH 7.

The overall stability constants (β_{MBA}^M) of $M(B)(ada)$ complexes may be obtained as computer output from which the step stability constants K_{MBA}^{MB} (equlm. 3, 4) and K_{MAB}^{MA} (equlm. 5) may be calculated using the relations (6) and (7), respectively, where, $A = ada^{3-}$:

$$\log K_{MBA}^{MB} = \log \beta_{MBA}^M - \log K_{MB}^M \quad (6)$$

($B = phen, bipy$)

$$\log K_{MAB}^{MA} = \log \beta_{MBA}^M - \log K_{MA}^M \quad (7)$$

($B = en, gly^-, ox^{2-}$)

The $\log K_{MA}^M$, $\log K_{MB}^M$ and most $\log \beta_{MAB}^M$ values (Table 1), as expected, fall in the Irving-Williams order³: $Co^{2+} < Ni^{2+} < Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$. However, the order: $Co^{2+} < Ni^{2+} > Cu^{2+} > Zn^{2+}$ of the $\log \beta_{MBA}^M$ and $\log K_{MBA}^{MB}$ values deviates from this general trend. For $Cu(phen)(ada)$ complex, the β_{MBA}^M and K_{MBA}^{MB} values are unexpectedly lower than those of the analogous Ni^{II} complexes. These deviations owe their origin in the tendency of $Cu^{2+}(d^9)$ to be distorted octahedral or square-planar due to inherent Jahn-Teller distortion⁴ particularly in the presence of strongly coordinating (N,N) bidentate phen and bipy ligands. As a result of this, the ada^{3-} anion which may coordinate as a (N,O⁻, O⁻,O⁻) quadridentate ligand in binary $M(ada)^-$ complexes ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}$) and also in ternary $M(B)(ada)^-$ complexes ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, B = phen, bipy$), possibly coordinates $Cu(phen)^{2+}$ and $Cu(bipy)^{2+}$ in glycinate (gly^-) like

Table-1. Proton-ligand constants and formation constants of binary and ternary M^{II} - H_3ada - B complexes ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn ; $B = phen, bipy, en, gly^-$ and ox^{2-}) in aqueous solution

$I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$), temp. = $25 \pm 1^\circ$

(a) Protonation constants of the ligands:

	H_3ada	$phenH_2^{2+}$	$bipyH_2^{2+}$	enH_2^{2+}	$HglyH^+$	H_2ox
pK_1^H	7.50	4.96	4.23	9.89	9.63	3.82
pK_2^H	3.09	1.90	1.32	7.10	2.41	1.26
pK_3^H	1.44	-	-	-	-	-

(b) M^{2+} - H_3ada (A) and M^{2+} -B binary constants:

A/B	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
$\log K_{MA}^M$ ada^{3-}	8.44	9.46	10.35	8.39
$\log K_{MB}^M$ phen	7.83	8.64	9.14	6.22
bipy	6.06	7.13	7.80	5.15
en	5.62	6.96	10.44	5.61
gly^-	4.75	5.73	8.23	4.96
ox^{2-}	3.33	3.83	4.49	3.48

(c) M^{2+} - H_3ada (A) -B ternary constants:

$\log \beta_{MAB}^M$	phen	14.14	17.70	16.91	13.20
bipy	13.82	14.52	15.57	10.97	
en	13.65	16.08	17.91	13.50	
gly^-	10.31	12.31	15.70	10.47	
ox^{2-}	8.89	10.41	11.96	8.99	
$\log K_{MBA}^{MB}$ phen	7.36	9.06	7.77	6.98	
bipy	7.76	7.39	7.77	5.82	
$\log K_{MAB}^{MA}$ en	5.21	6.62	7.56	5.11	
gly^-	1.87	2.85	5.35	2.08	
ox^{2-}	0.45	0.95	1.61	0.60	

Limits of error: $\pm(0.02-0.05)$ in log unit.

manner, i.e. as a (N,O⁻) bidentate ligand to produce the ternary $Cu(B)(ada)^-$ complexes ($B = phen, bipy$) in which Cu^{2+} adopts a square-planar $[Cu(N,N)(N,O^-)]$ or a distorted octahedral geometry. Interestingly, the $\log \beta_{Cu(B)(ada)}^{Cu}$ and $\log \beta_{Cu(B)(gly)}^{Cu}$ values ($B = phen, bipy$) are comparable (Table 2),

$$\Delta \log K_{Cu} =$$

$$\log \beta_{Cu(B)(gly)}^{Cu} - \log K_{Cu(B)}^{Cu} - \log K_{Cu(gly)}^{Cu} \quad (8)$$

using the statistically expected value of $\Delta \log K_{Cu}$ (-0.60 for square-planar coordination) and the experimental values of $\log K_{Cu(B)}^{Cu}$ and $\log K_{Cu(gly)}^{Cu}$. $\log K_{M(ada)(B)}^{M(ada)}$ values for B = en (N,N), gly⁻(N,O⁻) and ox²⁻(O⁻,O⁻) fall in the order :

Table 2

A	$\log \beta_{Cu(phen)(A)}^{Cu}$	$\log \beta_{Cu(bipy)(A)}^{Cu}$
ada ³⁻ (N,O ⁻ , O ⁻ ,O ⁻)	16.91	15.57
gly ⁻ (N,O ⁻)	16.77*	15.43*

*calculated on the basis of the relation (8)⁵.

en > gly⁻ >> ox²⁻ for all the four metal ions as expected, since the negative charge on the binary M(ada)⁻ complexes tends to repel the incoming negatively charged B ligands.

Fig. 1. pH-metric titration curves for 1 : 1 : 1 M^{II} : H₃ada : enH₂²⁺ ternary systems : (1) 0.01 M HNO₃; (2) (1) + 0.001 M Ni²⁺; (3) (1) + 0.001 M H₃ada; (4) (3) + 0.001 M Ni²⁺; (5) (1) + 0.001 M enH₂²⁺; (6) (5) + 0.001 M Ni²⁺; (7) (3) + 0.001 M Co²⁺ + 0.001 M enH₂²⁺; (8) (3) + 0.001 M Ni²⁺ + 0.001 M enH₂²⁺; (9) (3) + 0.001 M Cu²⁺ + 0.001 M enH₂²⁺; (10) (3) + 0.001 M Zn²⁺ + 0.001 M enH₂²⁺.

Experimental

The ligand, anthranilic acid *N,N*-diacetic acid (H₃ada) was prepared by condensing anthranilic acid (0.01 mol) with monochloroacetic acid (0.02 mol) in presence of Na₂CO₃ (0.05 mol) under refluxing condition in aqueous medium following the reported procedure⁶. The resulting mixture was cooled and acidified with HCl (pH ~2) when

H₃ada separated as white crystalline solid. The crude product was washed with cold water, crystallized from hot water and air-dried, m.p. 210° (Found : C, 52.25; H, 4.29; N, 5.71. Calcd. for : C, 52.17; H, 4.34; N, 5.53%); λ_{max} (H₂O) 223.5 nm; ν_{max} (KBr)⁷ 3671.7 (OH), 1728.3 (C=O), 1232.4 (C-N) cm⁻¹.

All other reagents were of A.R. quality and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO₂ free water. Metal nitrate solutions were prepared by dissolving alkali-free metallic hydroxides in nitric acid (A.R.) and the resulting solutions were standardized by combined acid-base, ion-exchange and complexometric EDTA titration⁸. The following series of mixtures were prepared for the equilibrium study : (i) 0.01 M HNO₃; (ii) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.001–0.002 M M^{II}(NO₃)₂; M = Co, Ni, Cu, Zn; (iii) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.001–0.005 M H₃ada; (iv) 0.01 M HNO₃ + 0.001–0.005 M H₂B; B = phen, bipy, en, gly⁻, ox²⁻; (v) (iii) + 0.001–0.002 M M^{II}(NO₃)₂; (vi) (iv) + 0.001–0.002 M M^{II}(NO₃)₂; (vii) (i) + 0.001 M H₃ada + 0.001 M H₂B + 0.001 M M^{II}(NO₃)₂. Initial volume of each mixture was 25 ml. Required amounts of NaNO₃ was added to each of these solutions to maintain the ionic strength fixed at *I* = 0.1 M. All the mixtures were allowed to attain equilibrium at 25 ± 1° (thermostated) and pH-metrically titrated with a carbonate-free standard 0.1 M NaOH solution⁹.

Analytical concentrations of H⁺ ion at different pH meter readings were calculated by the usual procedure¹⁰. pK_w of water at the experimental temperature and activity coefficient of H⁺ ion at the experimental ionic strength were obtained from literature¹¹. The proton-ligand and the metal-ligand constants were calculated using the SCOGS computer program² using the pH vs volume of NaOH data as were the averages of three titrations, each time repeating the cycle of operation upto the minimum value of standard deviation (i.e. 0.01 ml in the titrant). Complex formation equilibria were elucidated on the basis of the speciation curves.

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